

Farming at a loss: Who makes a loss from farming in Scotland and why do they continue to farm?

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Summary

Purpose:

This briefing report explores self-reported farm profitability trends (i.e. farmers' own assessments of their financial situation rather than official records) and influencing factors using data from the Farmer Intentions Survey (FIS) 2023, a large-scale telephone-based survey of 2,029 farmers, crofters, and other representatives of Scottish agriculture. Estimates of the percentage of farmers making a loss differ between the Farm Business Survey (FBS) and FIS differ due to factors such as weighting and variations in the types and sizes of farms surveyed. Additionally, profitability is self-reported in the FIS, whereas in the FBS farm business income is based on submitted accounts. Therefore, different results are to be expected.

This report focuses on three main research questions:

1. Who is making a loss from farming?
2. Why do they continue farming despite financial losses?
3. How do farmers plan to change their investment in farming in the future?

Main findings:

1. Who is making a loss from farming?

Younger and male farmers, as well as those managing arable or mixed farms, are less likely to report making a loss. In contrast, middle-aged farmers, women, new entrants, crofters, hobbyists, smallholders, and those on livestock or "Other" farms are most likely to report making a loss. Farmers involved in discussion groups, those who inherited their farms, or who have identified successors report were less likely to report losses.

2. Why do they continue farming despite financial losses?

Farmers might continue despite losses because making a profit is not always their main goal. Many rely on income sources other than farming to support their households. In addition, the fact that most farmers reporting losses still aim to break even or turn a profit suggests a strong attachment to farming as a way of life. suggesting financial gain is important but not necessarily the primary motivation for all farmers.

3. How do farmers plan to change their investment in farming in the future?

Farmers reporting losses tend to decrease capital expenditures and are about twice as likely to plan to sell up. In contrast, profitable farmers are more likely to invest in new technologies. This divergence illustrates how financial performance could influence strategic decisions.

2. Key Findings

What is the typical annual profit generated by the farming activity of your business/ holding?

Around 1 in 10 farmers report that they are operating at a loss. A further 2 in 10 break even. Additionally around one third of farmers make only between £1-£30,000 of profit a year from their farm business.

Figure 1. Percentage of the typical annual profit generated by farmers business/holding

1. Who is making a loss from farming?

a. Young farmers are the least likely to report making a loss and older farmers are more likely to report that they break even.

Figure 2. Self-reported annual profit across age groups

Approximately 6% of farmers aged 35 and under report operating at a loss, the lowest among all age groups, as shown in Figure 2. Meanwhile, 18% of young farmers report breaking even. Farmers aged 41–44 have the highest proportion reporting financial losses (19%), while roughly 17% report breaking even.

Older farmers (65+) are more likely to report breaking even than generating high profits. Among those aged 65–74, 7.5% report operating at a loss, while 19.6% report breaking even. Similarly, 7.5% of farmers aged 75 and over report losses, but around 27% report breaking even—the highest break-even rate among all age groups.

b. Different financial outcomes relate to variations in business goals between genders

Figure 3. Percentage of farmers with self-reported making a loss or breaking even based on gender

As shown in Figure 4, among male farmers, around 65% report that their primary aim is to make a profit, compared to 43% of female farmers. Meanwhile, a higher proportion of female farmers (36.3%) report breaking even, compared to 24% of male farmers. Additionally, 20.7% of female farmers report that making a profit is not their primary aim, compared to around 11% of male farmers. This suggests that financial motivations and operational priorities may differ by gender, potentially influencing self-reported profitability.

Taking all your sources of income into account, is making a profit the primary aim of this business/holding?

Figure 4. Percentage of farmers on self-reported making a profit is the primary aim of their business/holding based on gender

c. Farm type plays a crucial role in business/holdings income

Figure 5. Percentage of farmers with self-reported making a loss or breaking even according to farm type

Figure 5 demonstrates that self-reported financial outcomes vary by farm type. Arable farms are least likely to report a loss (6.8%) and less likely to report breaking even (16.5%). Meanwhile, "Other" farms (e.g. unclassified, horticulture, permanent crops, and poultry) report the highest financial risks. Livestock farms are more likely to report a loss (9.9%) and more likely to report breaking even (22%), meaning a substantial portion of livestock farmers sustain operations without making a profit. Mixed farms are also more likely to report breaking even (16.5%) and less likely to report a loss (8.6%), similar to arable farming.

d. Networks and experience contribute to financial success

Figure 6. Percentage of farmers with self-reported making a loss or breaking even depending on participation in formal/informal groups

As shown in Figure 6, farmers who engage in formal or informal discussion groups are less likely to report a loss (4.7%) compared to those who do not participate (11.8%). They are also less likely to report breaking even (11.7%) compared to non-participants (24.4%).

e. Financial outcomes are driven by farmer identities and intentions to make a profit

Figure 7. Percentage of farmers with self-reported typical annual profit by their farmer classification

Those who identify as farmers are least likely to report a loss (4.7%) and have a moderate self-reported break-even rate (14.4%), indicating greater financial stability and a higher likelihood of profitability compared to other classifications.

Figure 7 demonstrates that those identifying as crofters (17.8% loss, 34.2% break even), hobbyists (24.4% loss, 39.7% break even), and smallholders (24.1% loss, 38.0% break even) report the highest financial vulnerability. These groups often have smaller-scale operations, limited market access, and fewer financial resources, making profitability more challenging. A high self-reported break-even rate suggests many sustain operations without aiming for significant profits.

Those who identify as businesspeople have a relatively moderate financial position, with 10.1% reporting a loss and 13.8% breaking even. Finally, contractors are among the least likely to report a loss (5.3%) and have a low break-even rate (10.5%).

f. New entrants to farming are more likely to report making a loss than their experienced peers

Figure 8. Percentage of farmers' experience in farming (≤5 years vs. >5 years) according to their self-reported typical annual profit

As shown in Figure 8, the newer entrants face greater financial challenges. Among those managing farms for five years or less, around 24% report making a loss or just breaking even, while only around 11% report earning between £30,000–£100,000, and less than 1% report making over £100,000. In contrast, more experienced farmers (farming for over five years) show a higher concentration in self-reported profitable categories, with 34% reporting earnings up to £30,000 and 20.3% earning between £30,000–£100,000. This suggests that self-reported financial success in farming is strongly linked to long-term experience and sector stability.

2. Why do people continue farming despite making a loss?

a. Profit intentions drive farmers to continue despite losses

Is making a profit the primary aim of this business/holding?

- Yes
- No, but it is important that it breaks even
- No, making a profit is not the primary aim of this farm

A significant proportion of those reporting losses state that making a profit is not the primary aim of their farm. As shown in Figure 9, among those who report a loss, approximately 30% state that their primary aim is to make a profit.

Figure 9. Percentage of farmers with self-reported making a loss or breaking even depending on whether profit is their primary aim

In contrast, among farmers reporting a loss, around 38% state that making a profit is not their primary aim but that breaking even is important, while 32% do not consider profit-making a primary goal. Similarly, among those reporting breaking even, 41.7% aim to make a profit, 38.2% aim to break even, and 20% do not priorities profit-making.

b. The advantage for inherited farms could support farming continuation

- Make a loss
- Break even

Figure 10. Percentage of inherited vs. non-inherited farms in terms of self-reported making a loss or breaking even

Approximately 7% of farmers who report inheriting holdings also report making a loss, while around 17% report breaking even. In contrast, around 14% of farmers who have not inherited holdings report making a loss, and 26% report breaking even. This suggests a slight advantage for inherited farms, possibly due to the benefit of inherited experience or established operations. However, this comparison does not control for farm size or value, which might also influence the likelihood of continuation.

c. Farmers with a successor are more likely to maintain financial stability

Figure 11. Percentage of farmers with self-reported making a loss or breaking even depending on whether they have a successor

Farmers with a successor are more likely to maintain financial stability and make long-term investments, as only around 7% report a loss. Farmers without an identified successor are more likely to report making a loss (11.3%). The highest self-reported loss rate (13.8%) is among those who say it is "too early to decide" on a successor, highlighting potential instability or uncertainty in financial planning. Break-even rates are relatively similar across groups but slightly lower (19.7%) for those with a successor.

d. Unprofitable farmers often rely on other income sources to sustain their livelihoods

Figure 12. Dependence on farm income and self-reported financial performance

The data in Figure 12 highlights an inverse relationship between dependence on farm income and self-reported financial performance. Farmers who depend less on farming for household income are more likely to report operating at a loss, while those who depend on farming for over 75% of their income report the lowest loss rate (1.1%). Farmers continue farming even when they report a loss, which may be driven by non-financial motivations or they are not primarily focused on generating income. It's unclear why some farmers report a profit but indicate zero household income from their farm business. This might be due to their interpretation of "income" or how they handle reinvesting profits.

3. Understanding farmers future changes to investment intention.

a. Farmers facing loss have high intentions to increase holding size by 2028

Figure 13. Farmers' intentions to change business size in the next five years according to self-reported profit

Farmers who report not making a profit are about twice as likely to plan to sell up in the next five years (from 2023) compared to the most profitable farmers. However, the vast majority still intend to remain in farming. While uncertainty exists across different self-reported profitability levels, those earning over £100,000 are least likely to sell up and most likely to plan expansion (37%).

b. Farmers facing loss have highest intention to reduce capital investment until 2028

Farmers reporting financial losses are the most likely to plan to reduce capital investment in the next five years by 2028 (19.2%). However, around 34% intend to increase capital investment. Figure 14 demonstrates that those reporting breaking even are less likely to plan changes to capital investment, with around 60% planning to maintain current levels and 27% planning to increase investment.

Figure 14. Percentage of farmers who intend to invest in capital investment in the next five years according to their self-reported typical annual profit

Investment growth becomes more common as reported profitability rises, with the most profitable farms (£100,000+) having the highest percentage (47%) planning to invest more, while only 13% plan to reduce investment.

c. Losses don't stop farmers intention to invest in new technologies until 2028

Figure 15. Percentage of farmers who intend to invest in new technologies in the next five years according to their self-reported typical annual profit

Around 8% of farmers reporting financial losses plan to reduce investment in new technologies, while 27.6% intend to increase investment, as shown in Figure 15. Those reporting breaking even show a similar pattern, with 7% planning to decrease and 24% planning to increase investment. As reported profitability rises, so does the likelihood of intending to invest in new technologies, with around 46% of those earning between £30,000–£100,000 and 62% of those earning over £100,000 planning to increase their investment.

Conclusions

1. Who is making a loss from farming?

- Farmers' age is co-related to financial performance. Older farmers may benefit from assistance to retire. Younger farmers, particularly those who have not inherited their holdings, may benefit from targeted supports.
- Male farmers are less likely to report financial losses, while female farmers have a higher break-even rate. Approximately twice the proportion of female farmers report that making a profit is not their primary aim compared to male farmers. Therefore, targeted support for women farmers may help address the gender gap in financial success, especially if these farmers are more focused on profitability. This may be important to prevent potential exits from farming due to financial pressures.
- Arable and mixed farms demonstrate greater financial stability, while livestock and "Other" farms face higher financial risks.
- Farmers who participate in networks tend to report better financial performance, suggesting that knowledge exchange may contribute to improved outcomes.
- New entrants to farm management tend to face greater financial challenges, with higher rates of loss and break-even compared to experienced farmers.

2. Why do they continue farming despite financial losses?

- Many farmers continue farming despite financial losses because profit-making is not always their primary goal.
- The advantage of inherited farms may support farming continuation, as farmers who inherit their holdings are less likely to report losses to continue.
- The percentage of farmers with an identified successor who report making a loss is nearly half that of those without one. Farmers with a successor may be more motivated to sustain their business for future generations and invest in long term growth.
- Some farmers remain in farming despite financial losses because farming is not their primary source of household income. For those who rely less on farm income, alternative income sources may help sustain their farming operations.

3. How do farmers plan to change their farming practices in the future?

- Farmers operating at a loss are significantly more likely to consider leaving farming within the next five years compared to highly profitable farmers. However, the majority still intend to continue farming, maintaining or increasing the size of business and holdings by 2028.
- A substantial number of farmers plan to maintain or increase their capital investment by 2028.
- The majority of farmers intend to maintain or increase their investment in new technologies, regardless of their financial performance. Even among those operating at a loss, a significant proportion plan to invest in innovation, with the likelihood of increased investment rising as profitability improves.

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